

Simplifying Square Roots of Complex Numbers via Scalar-Based Factorization

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a novel method of simplifying the roots of complex numbers in the form of $\sqrt{a + bi}$ where a and b are real numbers. Traditional methods, such as algebraic manipulation and polar form conversion, typically involve multiple complex steps and are prone to calculation errors. The proposed method introduces a scalar k that factors the complex number inside the root, allowing it to be rewritten as the square of another complex number. This approach significantly reduces computational complexity and minimizes the risk of calculation errors. Examples are provided to demonstrate the method's principles and efficiency in comparison to traditional solutions.

INTRODUCTION

The calculation of square roots of complex numbers, represented in the form $\sqrt{a + bi}$, is a crucial concept in mathematics with applications across fields such as engineering, physics, and computer science. The process traditionally involves three main methods: solving a system of equations algebraically or converting the complex number into its polar form. While both methods can be used in most cases, they involve many complex steps that require additional knowledge or memorization of intricate steps, especially when the numbers are large and difficult to compute. Effective methods are needed to provide an easier and faster process for solving such equations.

This paper introduces a novel method for simplifying complex square roots so that they can be easily solved without using a system of equations or polar form. By calculating a scalar k , we can transform the equation into a more manageable form and solve it using the quadratic formula. This method reduces the computational burden and provides a more intuitive approach to solving these equations, particularly for educational purposes and computational applications.

The purpose of this work is to present the method in an understandable way, providing examples of its implementation and explaining its effectiveness in comparison with current methods.

METHODOLOGY

To understand how the method in this paper works lets start with a basic example of a complex square root in the form $a + bi$, such as $\sqrt{3 - 4i}$. This complex number can be rewritten as the square of another complex number, which allows us to easily extract the square root.

$$\sqrt{3 - 4i} = \sqrt{(2 - i)^2} = \pm (2 - i)$$

However, not every root can be straightforwardly rewritten in this form. For instance, with the root $\sqrt{24 - 7i}$ we cannot use this technique for simplifying. In such cases, we are typically forced to use either algebraic manipulation, which involves solving a system of equations, or convert the complex number into its polar form to find the square root.

Nevertheless, if we introduce one additional step, we can simplify the process. To represent the equation in a more convenient form, we introduce the scalar k which allows us to factor the square root and simplify the expression. In this case this scalar $k = \frac{1}{2}$, and using this value, the final expression simplifies to:

$$\sqrt{24 - 7i} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(48 - 14i)} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \times \sqrt{48 - 14i} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \times \sqrt{(7 - i)^2} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (7 - i)$$

The main challenge in applying this method is determining the value of k , which is necessary for simplifying the square root. Fortunately, k can be calculated using a relatively simple formula:

$$k = \frac{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2} - a}{2}$$

To understand where this formula derives from, we need to recognize a recurring pattern in the square roots of certain complex numbers of the form $\sqrt{a + bi}$, such as $\sqrt{3 - 4i}$. If we examine examples of such roots that can be expressed in square form without factoring, we find that they

are always equal to $\sqrt{(\frac{b}{2} + i)^2}$. For example:

$$\sqrt{3 - 4i} \Rightarrow a = 3; b = -4$$

$$\sqrt{a + bi} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{b}{2} + i\right)^2} \Rightarrow \sqrt{3 - 4i} = \sqrt{\left(-\frac{4}{2} + i\right)^2} = \sqrt{(-2 + i)^2} = \pm (2 - i)$$

From the example above, we observe that to express the square root in this simplified form, we need to find a pair of values for a and b such that:

$$a + bi = \left(\frac{b}{2} + i\right)^2 \Rightarrow a + bi = \left(\frac{b}{2}\right)^2 + bi + i^2 \Rightarrow \left(\frac{b}{2}\right)^2 - 1 = a$$

To apply this method to a root that cannot be directly rewritten in square form, we can factor the complex number to obtain more convenient values for c and d values where $c = \frac{a}{k}$ and $d = \frac{b}{k}$. This transformation simplifies the original complex number, allowing us to work with easier components. Therefore, we can calculate the scalar k used for factoring by the following equation:

$$\left(\frac{b}{2k}\right)^2 - 1 = \frac{a}{k}$$

$$\frac{b^2}{4k^2} - \frac{a}{k} - 1 = 0$$

$$\frac{b^2}{4k^2} - \frac{ak}{k^2} - \frac{k^2}{k^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{b^2/4}{k^2} - \frac{ak}{k^2} - \frac{k^2}{k^2} = 0$$

$$k^2 + ak - \frac{b^2}{4} = 0$$

$$D = a^2 + b^2 \Rightarrow k_1 = \frac{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2} - a}{2}; k_2 = \frac{-\sqrt{a^2 + b^2} - a}{2};$$

At this step, either of the roots of k can be used, but it is easier to work with the positive root to extract it from the square root as a positive factor. For simplicity, we choose the positive root k_1 and use it as a general value in our method. When we apply the formula to $\sqrt{24 - 7i}$, which we have already solved before, we find that the formula provides the applicable value $k = \frac{1}{2}$:

$$k = \frac{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2} - a}{2} = \frac{\sqrt{24^2 + 7^2} - 24}{2} = \frac{25 - 24}{2} = \frac{1}{2}$$

One more example of utilizing this method with the square root $\sqrt{16 - 30i}$:

$$k = \frac{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2} - a}{2} = \frac{\sqrt{16^2 + 30^2} - 16}{2} = 9$$

$$\sqrt{16 - 30i} = \sqrt{9 \left(\frac{16}{9} - \frac{30i}{9} \right)} = 3 \sqrt{\left(\frac{16}{9} - \frac{10i}{3} \right)} = 3 \sqrt{\left(-\frac{5}{3} + i \right)^2} = \pm (5 - 3i)$$

The equation is solved in just two lines, comparable to solving a simple quadratic equation. In contrast to the formula for the square root of a complex number, our approach eliminates the need to memorize a long sequence of variables. Instead, it only requires remembering a simple formula for calculating the scalar k .

If we compare our method to the two other common approaches for calculating complex square roots:

- **Algebraic manipulation** involves solving a system of equations, which requires multiple steps and increases the chances of making mistakes during calculations.
- **Converting to polar form** adds complexity by requiring trigonometric knowledge, further complicating the process.

Our method offers a more straightforward, intuitive alternative that minimizes the risk of errors and simplifies the overall process.

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